

Executive Summary

Virtual Reality and Education: The Use of Simulated Classrooms for Professional Development of Teachers

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Background

Classroom organisation and management are widely recognised as major sources of stress for teachers and a leading cause of attrition among newly qualified educators^{1,2}. Initial Teacher Education (ITE) often lacks opportunities for students to practice classroom management in realistic settings³. Virtual Reality (VR) offers a potential solution by providing immersive, controllable, and repeatable environments for experiential learning⁴.

VR has been successfully applied in other professional training contexts⁵ and is characterised by three key features: full immersion, artificial environments, and user interactivity⁴. While VR has demonstrated effectiveness in teaching technical skills⁶, its application to socially complex and emotionally rich settings such as classrooms remains limited⁷⁻⁹. Previous research has shown VR can foster empathy and reflection in teacher education^{10,11}, but no known studies have examined its role in improving classroom organisation and management. This study aimed to address this gap by investigating the following research question:

- Can VR simulated classroom environments provide a medium for professional development and reflection for teachers regarding classroom organisation and management?

Methods

A constructivist, multi-method design was adopted¹², incorporating stakeholder participation and aligning with the ADDIE instructional design framework¹³. Data collection occurred in two stages. Stage 1 involved semi-structured interviews with in-practice teachers to identify themes influencing classroom organisation and management. Eight themes and sixty codes emerged, including cultural influences, school organisation, teacher approach, physical adaptation, work adaptation, learning atmosphere, engagement and ownership, and pupil-teacher relationships. These insights informed the development of three different simulated classrooms, each reflecting different pedagogical orientations—learning-centred, learner-centred, and teacher-centred.

Stage 2 involved 16 participants from four categories: preservice teachers, in-practice teachers, retired teachers, and ITE educators. Participants explored the three VR classrooms using Oculus Quest headsets. Participants completed tasks under a Think Aloud protocol, followed by semi-structured interviews. Qualitative data were analysed through thematic coding and triangulated across methods¹⁴. The analysis combined content analysis of verbalised thoughts during VR sessions with thematic interpretation of interview responses.

Key Findings

Participants engaged most with themes related to physical adaptation, such as desk layout, space to move, and resource accessibility. Codes relating to group work, technology, and pupil access to resources were most frequently discussed in the learning-centred classroom, while behaviour management dominated discussions among retired and in-practice teachers. Preservice teachers emphasised the importance of dedicated areas for specialist activities. External influences such as government policy were rarely mentioned, suggesting that classroom organisation decisions are primarily shaped by personal experience rather than systemic factors.

Triangulation with interviews confirmed that participants' preferences aligned broadly with the pedagogical intent of each simulated classroom. Retired teachers favoured teacher-centred layouts for behaviour control, while preservice teachers preferred flexible, learner-centred environments. ITE educators demonstrated the most engagement with pedagogical terminology, reflecting their academic orientation. Participants highlighted the immersive nature of VR and its ability to stimulate reflective thinking about classroom design. However, concerns were raised about cost, technical challenges, and the inability of VR to fully replicate the complexity of live classroom dynamics. A minority reported discomfort in the introductory environment, underscoring the need for careful design to minimise cybersickness.

Conclusions and Implications

The findings suggest that VR simulations can provide meaningful opportunities for reflection and discussion about classroom organisation and management. While VR cannot replace real-world teaching experience, it offers a safe, repeatable, and adaptable environment for exploring pedagogical strategies. Integration of VR into ITE could enhance preparedness for classroom challenges, provided that implementation addresses cost, accessibility, and technical limitations.

The immersive quality of VR enabled participants to reflect on complex social issues such as pupil-teacher relationships and engagement strategies. While physical fidelity appeared to enhance presence, its direct impact on learning outcomes remains uncertain. Participants' choices were influenced more by personal experience than by formal ITE training, reinforcing the need for tools that bridge theory and practice. VR offers such a bridge, providing opportunities for reflection and experimentation in a controlled environment. Future research should explore the transferability of skills learned in VR to real-world contexts.

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